

THE ESSENCE OF GENDER MODELS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL THINKING OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract. In this article, the necessity and prospects of improving the system of training future pedagogues based on the gender approach, and opinions on the regular improvement of knowledge and skills related to the development of women's opportunities are described.

Key words: Gender equality, globalization conditions, gender differences, social necessity, continuous education, individual qualities, educational standards.

Introduction.

One of the most important achievements in the field of pedagogy today is the expansion of opportunities for education based on gender equality and differences. This phenomenon has special value from the point of view of humanitarianization of education. In the process of realizing this goal, the first task is to improve existing educational programs using new pedagogical technology and modern methods. Gender equality in improved curricula, as well as design of teaching materials in all subjects on the basis of gender equality and differences, are of great importance. Such an educational process requires the creation of new educational tools - methodical materials and didactic developments. In turn, educational and methodical materials should be selected in connection with the means of control.

Although the concept of "gender" means sexes, gender relations, in recent years it has become a social reality that applies to almost all disciplines. "The term gender was first introduced into the scientific literature by the American researcher-scientist J. Scott, and the expected goal was to interpret the interaction of men and women in society from a social point of view.

The educational system is a mirror that reflects the society as a whole, it has its influence on it, and in turn, the changes taking place in education do not fail to affect the development of the society. Therefore, the educational system should be the initiator of changes in the implementation of gender equality in society.

This, in turn, requires the development of the theoretical and methodological foundations of the implementation and management of the gender approach to the higher education system. Because the stable progress and development of every country depends on the human factor, especially the scientific, creative and spiritual potential of the young generation.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on the gender approach, researches in areas such as improving the quality of education in continuing education institutions, developing women's social activity, gender issues in professional education were implemented. In these studies, the issues of increasing the social activity of women were analyzed through a gender approach, and the issues of the gender approach in pedagogical education were studied. According to scientists, the process of developing gender aspects and principles of implementation in teacher training is the main stage that brings them to the final result. A teacher who understands gender aspects can create an opportunity for the young generation to think and act consciously due to their awareness and sensitivity to gender issues. Therefore, the movement to implement gender equality in education should begin with the teacher and cover his entire activity, from the stage of professional training to the stage of continuous professional development. Therefore, in higher education institutions, in addition to professional knowledge and skills, students should develop important life skills, including analytical and critical thinking skills, problem solving, flexibility, interpersonal communication skills, as well as independent and cooperative work training is very important for the formation of gender competence. For this, it is necessary to implement a gender approach to the higher education system and develop effective mechanisms for its management.

A gender approach is an approach to understanding the existence of gender inequality and their causes and consequences, as well as providing solutions to them. A gender approach is a change in gender relations between men and women, which promotes a more equal distribution of powers and responsibilities that have beneficial effects on both men and women. The gender approach in the training of future teachers includes the direct involvement of gender issues in the development of an educational strategy, in determining the content and technologies of professional training, in the development of professional competencies of teachers, in the implementation of scientific research. In our opinion, the implementation of a gender approach to the higher education system involves all components of the educational process, i.e. educational, educational (educational content) and methodical (teaching methods, organization of the

educational process, pedagogical cooperation) aspects, as well as organizational-pedagogical conditions, management of the educational system, it is intended to increase the effectiveness of gender issues.

Gender similarity - arising as a result of the process of mutual cooperation between "I" and others, serves the psychological and pedagogical adaptation of male and female characteristics. It helps to develop the social activity of students based on the gender approach. The subjects taught in higher education create an opportunity to increase the social activity of students and perfect the process of adaptation to society. Currently, the educational importance of social institutions such as family, education, religion, culture in the development of students' social activity increases the effectiveness of this process.

It was understood that if the valuable orientations, goals and norms of modern education are included along with the qualities known and accepted in the society, such as "femininity", "masculinity", it will in some sense be a school seen on a new gender basis.

When these values, goals and norms are included in the "final result" of the activity of the educational institution, it is possible to talk about the expansion of the meaning of this concept, the introduction of new "specific characteristics" of students, and also about the correction of the educational process.

In our country, the appearance of Uzbek girls is one of the main requirements of national education. Good behavior is not only the theoretical basis of morals, beauty, work and other education of girls, but also the application of this level of education in their personal life. The greatest responsibility falls on the father and mother. At this point, it should be emphasized that the mother is the main influencing force in the education of girls. In most peoples, the father is busy with the family's economic affairs, in addition to meeting and providing for the material needs of the family. This is a fact known from the history of Uzbek families and a tradition inherited from our ancestors. Accordingly, more mothers are with the child.[1] It is not for nothing that the proverb "What goes in with milk comes out with the soul" is said in our people. However, in the future, some families in our society may encounter negative situations regarding child upbringing. If we look at the pedagogical consequences of the issue, it is manifested in the complaints of some parents about their children's lack of love. For example, most parents have the same opinion about their children's bad behavior: "they don't stick to what they know, they don't know how to respect." The social reasons for this are manifested in parents' neglect of child education. Children with parents and relatives are also transferred to the "House of Mercy".

This is contrary to the values of our ancestors, who followed the principle of "If there are ten, replace another".

In particular, the derailment of girls' education has negative consequences. As long as the knowledge and experience of ensuring the continuity of family life and the life of the nation in educating Uzbek girls, as long as knowledge, skills and abilities are not transferred from ancestors to generations, both family life and social life will suffer degradation (crisis). goes Therefore, the upbringing and experiences of mothers to girls have been and will be a requirement of the necessary needs to find their place in family and social life. If girls acquire the qualities of a socially active person from an early age, they will in turn become perfect mothers and well-rounded individuals. Therefore, it can be concluded that in fact, the development of every nation depends on the upbringing of socially active and quality girls.

In their research on the system of Uzbek national moral values, scientists have partially studied the problems of girls' spirituality and upbringing in connection with specific issues. Thus, the study of the historical pedagogical conditions of the organization of gender-differentiated education in the Uzbek national education system significantly enriches the effectiveness of the implementation of the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" and improves the strategic problems of youth education, including the effectiveness of pedagogical technologies. Most authors mainly study the content of the traditional pedagogical heritage of the people and only then consider the individual as an object of the educational process. However, we believe that it is necessary to improve the methods and mechanisms of applying this experience in the practical activities of the developing society. In addition, it should be noted that the education of girls in the field of pedagogy is mainly limited to learning from the point of view of preparation for family life.

There are several studies in the field of Uzbek ethnopedagogy, but the study of the characteristics of girls' education, the research of the theoretical and practical content of the process of forming a girl's personality, based on the national and cultural characteristics of different regions of our country, the characteristics and traditions of modern girls' education there is a need to study, model the program of implementing the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" based on the traditions of the Uzbek people, and study the possibilities of increasing the effectiveness of its application in the process of forming modern girls.

It reveals the rich source of learning and understanding the characteristics of the national education system of the Uzbek people, the experience of universal education. In this regard, the historical pedagogical experience of the education of Uzbek girls, which until recently has been left out of the attention of scientific pedagogical research, has very rich methodological approaches. In this section of the dissertation, an attempt was made to study the characteristics of girls' education in the Uzbek national pedagogical culture and the possibilities of using it in modern educational practice.

In order to clarify the main goal of our research, we believe that it is necessary to introduce the concept of "differentiation of education" taking into account gender differences. We use the concepts of "gender" and "gender differentiation" in our research. The gender approach to education consists in taking into account the multifaceted influence of the gender factor, which includes several aspects of this characteristic: biological sex, gender role stereotypes, gender norms, and the specificity of the gender role. Psychological and neurophysiological knowledge determined by the biological element are specific characteristics of boys and girls. The social environment is an important factor in the formation and development of the personality of boys and girls, men and women. The social and cultural components of the concepts of "gender", "gender differences", "gender differentiation" are the latest directions of modern scientific research and serve as conditions for the reconstruction (reconstruction) of girls' education and gender differentiation. . The concept of "gender differentiation of education" is used in the context of the concepts of "sexual differentiation of education", "differentiation taking into account gender differences" and "choosing the content, tools and methods of education based on the gender characteristics of a boy or girl". The term "gender" has a broader meaning than the word "sex" and has become an objective term of modern scientific language. It should be noted that the ratio and definition of the concepts of "sex" and "gender" have not yet been fully popularized, so we believe that the concept of "gender" can be determined by specific national, cultural, psychological and psychophysiological characteristics of biological sex. we count. Thus, in this study, the concepts of "differentiation of education" are close to each other, taking into account "gender differentiation", "gender gap" and "gender difference".

It is evident that there are not enough educational materials for developing gender culture, including methodical manuals in the field of spiritual education, necessary textbooks for students. In order to prevent and eliminate these shortcomings, further development of the national-spiritual education system

through the development of gender culture is of great importance. In this regard, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated: "Our main goal is to create all opportunities for our children to fully realize their talents and abilities, noble aspirations, increase their social activity, and take a worthy place in life."

Regarding these thoughts of the President, today in our country, the work on protection of family, motherhood and childhood, women's rights and interests, improvement of women's working and living conditions, and ensuring gender equality is being consistently continued. In particular, a new system was introduced to improve the conditions for girls growing up in low-income families to get an education. In accordance with this system, 940 additional places were allocated to full-time departments of higher educational institutions during the academic year for such girls on the basis of a state grant. Of course, the reforms implemented in the field of education within the framework of the development of gender culture in our country, in turn, will create a foundation for the future development of our country.

Today, in our country, special tasks have been defined regarding the issue of turning gender culture into the main factor of development. The progressive youth of Uzbekistan are achieving remarkable achievements in various fields and on a global scale thanks to the purposeful, continuous education of the state and their parents. is doing. Education and upbringing cannot be separated from each other, only when these two processes are organized on a harmonious, continuous basis, a person is polite, moral, highly spiritual, and at the same time knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally and physically healthy. , bringing up patriotic young people with a broad worldview and thinking, possessing modern professions, was mentioned. At the same time, the integration of youth education in Uzbekistan, that is, the coordination of education and training, the formation of scientific-based basic competencies and qualities based on the needs of today, the improvement of the effectiveness of education and training, and the main factor of modern personnel training, are of great importance. is given importance.

A new, systematic approach to education, the formation of young men and women as active individuals, family, pre-school education, general secondary, vocational education, higher educational institutions, social-pedagogical possibilities of neighborhoods and their sets the highest goal of raising the scientific-methodical integrity to a new level. Further development of spiritual education through effective implementation of education is of particular importance.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it is necessary to protect the mind and thinking of young men and women from harmful influences, and fill the gaps by directing their inner world towards perfection. Carrying out all these good works, of course, our teachers and coaches who have enough knowledge and skills, to be more precise, is one of the main tasks of education. In this educational process, it is necessary to promote our spiritual values, unique customs and activities of the Uzbek people, and prepare the ground for each of them to occupy a unique position.

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